

nanoTrek® - Quantum Tunneling Linear Encoder

for Sub-nanometer Positional Metrology with Centimeters Range

M.T. Michalewicz^{*}, P. Glowacki^{*}, N. Singh^{**}, S. Balakumar^{**} and N. N. Gosvami^{***}

^{*}Quantum Precision Instruments Asia Pte Ltd, 14A Prince George's Park, Singapore 118413,
marek@quantum-pi.com, piotr@quantum-pi.com

^{**}Institute of Microelectronics, 11 Science Road, Singapore 117685, navab@ime.a-star.edu.sg,

^{***}Department of Mechanical Engineering, National University of Singapore, 9 Engineering Drive 1
Singapore 117576, ngosvami@nus.edu.sg

ABSTRACT

Realisation of the first working linear encoder based on quantum tunneling between arrays of nanowires is presented. The sensing element consists of 12,000 nanowires, each 90 nm wide and 5 mm long, on an area of 5 x 4.3 mm. The sensing element was fabricated using phase shift mask lithography and dry etch processes followed by CMP; characterisation was carried with SEM and AFM. Finally transduction mechanism, showing linear encoder performance was demonstrated with electrical testing using independent nanopositioner. Strong signals in μA range are obtained on scans from several hundred nm to several mm range. *nanoTrek*® may address problems of dimensional metrology and alignment at the next technology nodes in micro-fabrication, nano-positioning and nano-imprinting.

Keywords: quantum tunneling, NEMS, positional metrology, linear encoder, tunneling sensors

1 MOTIVATION

Sub-nanometer dimensional metrology is critical to advance microelectronic manufacturing below the 100 nm critical dimensions limit, and then on to the next nodes defined by Sematech International: 65 nm and 45 nm. Metrology tools to reach those next nodes are not well developed. New sub-nanometer metrology solutions and new technology is required [1]. Quantum- π proprietary technology [2,3] is well suited to offer those solutions and to provide the necessary metrology tools. Nanometer and sub-nanometer scale positional metrology is also critical to advancements in nanotechnology, in general.

2 *nanoTrek*® CONCEPT

Quantum- π technology utilizes physical phenomenon of *electron tunneling*. Quantum electron tunneling occurs when two electrical conductors are placed in a very close proximity to each other and are separated by an insulating layer. When small bias potential is applied between

conductors, electric current flows between them despite no apparent “presence or availability” of electric carriers in the gap region. Quantum tunneling is an exceedingly sensitive probe of inter-electrode separation, electrode area, the type of electrode material and the nature of intervening insulator. *Quantum- π technology is based on variable overlap area of the electrodes.*

A generic Quantum- π *nanoTrek*® device is composed of two plates separated by a very thin layer of soft-matter spacer insulator. Several hundred to several thousand nanowires are fabricated on each substrate. The nanowires on the two surfaces facing each other and aligned with each other form elongated electrodes in the tunneling process. Substrates are allowed to slide past each other *while their normal separation remains constant* – this makes our device distinctly different from any previously built tunneling sensors where cantilevers and tips were critical elements and it was variable inter-electrode separation that produced transduction signal. Any lateral shift of substrates with nanowires will induce change in alignment and that in turn will result in measurable changes of electrical current flowing between the plates. This effect is demonstrated on Figures 1 and 2.

Figure 1: Idealised device showing strips of conductors perfectly overlapping each other (top projection at left panel, cross section at middle panel, max current – right panel).

Figure 2: Idealised device showing strips of conductors in off-set position (top projection at left panel, cross section at middle panel, results in no current – right panel).

3 FABRICATION

The fabrication of the presented *nanoTrek* is done at Institute of Microelectronics, Singapore using 8” Semiconductor processing line. Due to less prone for native oxide growth – better tunneling effects -- Tantalum Nitride is used as the metal of choice. The sub-100 nm lines at 360 nm pitch were patterned using KrF Nikon lithography scanner with alternating phase shift mask. Dry etching was used to transfer the resist patterns into the metal layer which was followed by USG deposition and CMP for planarization.

“To illustrate the sort of nanosystems Quantum- π develops imagine a rectangular plot of land 50km by 43km on each side; absolutely flat, so flat and even, that there is no vertical protrusion, no bump larger than 2 cm on the entire area. Now imagine a straight path 1 meter wide running the entire length of 50km, and another one, separated by 2.7 meter, and another one... Imagine 12,000 such 1 meter wide and 50 km long paths! Now, shrink this picture ten million times and you get an image of one of the hundreds of nanoTrek® devices fabricated in Singapore. The plot of land is a chip of silicon wafer, the paths are metallic nanowires which are about one hundredth of a width of a human hair.”

3.1 SEM characterisation

The fabricated *nanoTrek* were physically characterized using X-section SEM and AFM. The SEM image in Fig. 4 clearly shows the well defined nanowires imbedded in dielectric layers.

Figure 3: Tilt view SEM image of TaN metal lines – nanowires – before planarization.

Figure 4: X-section SEM image of TaN nanowires. Width of nanowires is nominally 90 nm. Pitch is 360 nm.

3.2 AFM characterisation

Topography imaging of the sample was performed in air using a commercial AFM (Molecular Imaging Corp.) in contact mode using a silicon nitride cantilever ($K=0.36$ N/m). The left image shows the topography of the sample while the right image shows the friction signal.

Figure 5. The AFM scans confirm SEM characterisation: well defined nanowires of width 90 nm are separated by 270 nm wide strips of insulator. The conducting nanowires are slightly below insulating strips surface, with 15 nm maximum variation in height. This experiment can in itself be considered almost a “realisation” of the Canon Patent “Encoder using the tunnel current effect” [4]

4 ELECTRICAL CHARACTERISATION

The electrical testing was performed in cleanroom Class 1,000 environment at Institute of Materials Research and Engineering, Singapore by Quantum- π .

Test setup consists of a mechanical die holder, a nanopositioner, which facilitates movement, Keithley 2400 SourceMeter supplying bias voltage, and measuring the current, and a computer that runs control software.

Small DC bias voltage is applied to the chips, causing tunnel current flow. For each sample we first measure I-V characteristic, to confirm that the observed current is not Ohmic. In each case studied we observed highly non-linear, typical of tunneling I-V characteristic. We applied reverse bias and varied Voltage between -3 to 3 Volts. In several runs we applied up to 20V potential. The dies are separated by a commercial organic nanolubricant. We expect it to exert some influence when we reverse bias. While one of the dies is stationary, the other is moved in lateral direction so the mutual normal separation between the chips is kept

constant, but the plates move laterally in the direction essentially perpendicular to the nanowires.

5 RESULTS

5.1 I-V characteristics

The figure below illustrates typical I-V characteristic of stationary *nanoTrek*. Please note that the curve is strongly non-linear, which is consistent with theoretical characteristics of tunneling current.

Figure 5. I-V characteristic of *nanoTrek*.

5.2 I(x) characteristics

Linear encoder function of the *nanoTrek* is clearly visible here. As the plates move in small steps (40nm in this example) the current varies strongly. Note that *nanoTrek* is digital-analog encoder in a sense, that the peak-to-peak separation (digital signal) is defined by the physical pitch of the device, but the signal can also be resolved *along the slopes of peaks* – and hence, in principle, with appropriate signal analysis it can have sub-nanometer (analog) resolution. (Of course, by analogy to quadrature noncontact optical or magnetic encoders, quad, binary or Gray code tunneling encoders can be realised.)

Figure 6. I(x) characteristic.

Uneven height of current peaks is attributed to tick-slip effect due to imperfections of mechanical setup. There is also an effect of quantization as the movement is discrete, not continuous. We are studying these effects, and the ways to avoid them in the next generation of the devices.

5.3 Computer modeling results

We have run computer simulations for signal produced from two overlapping grids of 12,000 lines with geometry such as our fabricated samples. The figure below represents two runs: line A (solid line) represents two perfectly aligned grids (angle of rotation $\alpha=0$) passing each other with lateral step size 27nm; line B (broken line) represents two arrays rotated with respect of each other by $\sim 0.22^\circ$ passing each other with the same step of 27nm.

Figure 7. Computer simulations of *nanoTrek* scans – compare with experimental results of Figure 6.

6 FUTURE – WHAT NEXT?

We have demonstrated fabrication processes, a physical embodiment and a proof-of-concept of a tunneling linear encoder. We are continuing performance testing, new fabrication methods, and variety of different applications for our generic *nanoTrek* devices in Singapore and elsewhere. With microfabrication technology available, e.g. nanoimprint lithography, we can fabricate nanowires of sever nanometers width and several millimeters long on sensing areas of centimeters. This will allow construction of tunneling linear encoders with sub-nanometer resolution and centimeter range – a metrology devices for the next microfabrication nodes.

If we add a timer to this device we can create NEMS-type devices (*without MEMS fabbing – as our process is planar and requires only few masks*) and that will give raise to entire family of motion sensors : sensors that measure changes of motion in time (velocity) and changes of velocity in time (acceleration) and all derived physical quantities, e.g. flow meters, microphones, vibration sensors, accelerometers, gyroscopes and many others. Our

metrology devices and motion sensors are being currently tested by several corporations at their facilities.

REFERENCES

- [1] C. Merzbacher, "National Nanotechnology Initiative from a Policy Perspective: Where are we and where are we going?" Executive Office of the President of the United States, presented at Nanotech 2005, Anaheim, pp.13-17
- [2] Marek Michalewicz, "Tunnelling current between two quasi-1-dimensional conductors", Eighth Foresight Conference on Molecular Nanotechnology, November 3-5, 2000 (poster)
- [3] M. T. Michalewicz, US Patent 6,707,308
- [4] European Patent 94120561.9, Yanagisawa Y. et al. Canon Kabushiki Kaisha, 1988